

UNCOVERING THE ROLE OF BUILDING ORIENTATION AND STRESS RATIO ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF L-PBF Ti6Al4V MINIATURISED STRUT-LIKE LATTICE SPECIMENS

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Metal additive manufacturing has revolutionised the production of intricate components for specialised applications, such as prosthetic devices or aircraft components. This innovation also stems from the ability to effortlessly fabricate architected cellular materials, a new class of engineering materials with tailorable mechanical properties. However, challenges in structural integrity and standardisation still persist, impacting lattice-based component performances. Fatigue behaviour in lattice structures remains a critical concern, particularly at the millimetre/sub-millimetre scale, an aspect that has not yet received adequate attention. This study examines miniaturised Laser-Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) Ti6Al4V thin-strut specimens under diverse loading conditions and building orientations. The impact of the latter on the mean stress sensitivity is assessed by using Haigh diagrams. Additionally, suitable mean stress predictive models and buckling instability regions are explored to enable a more informed lattice design.

Keywords: Metal Additive Manufacturing, Lattice structures, Mean Stress Effect, Building Orientation

INTRODUCTION

Metal Additive Manufacturing (MAM), particularly Laser-Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF), has brought about a transformative shift in the production of intricate components, offering opportunities for innovative designs and customised mechanical properties (du Plessis et al. [1]). Despite the advantages presented by MAM, concerns about structural integrity (Willemsen et al. [2]) and regulatory deficiencies (Ricles et al. [3]) pose significant challenges to its widespread adoption.

A critical step in addressing these concerns revolves around enhancing the fatigue resistance of lattice-based structures. Fatigue, a multifaceted phenomenon, is profoundly influenced by inherent manufacturing errors associated with the L-PBF process (Hossain et al. [4] and Maleki et al. [5]). While there has been substantial attention given to macro-scale fatigue properties, it is crucial to recognise that fatigue predominantly occurs at the local scale. This is where the specific arrangement and design of interconnected struts within the lattice structure play a pivotal role in influencing stress distributions and crack propagation pathways. Delving into local-scale fatigue phenomena, such as the behaviour of individual struts or junctions, enables us to pinpoint vulnerable areas prone to fatigue failure. Previous studies (Romano et al. [6], Dzugan et al. [7], Pehlivan et al. [8], Pegues et al. [9] and Yin et al. [10]) have demonstrated the detrimental impact of surface texture/roughness, surface, and sub-surface defects, combined with the specimen “size effect” on fatigue properties at a

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miniaturised scale. Furthermore, it is well-established that the orientation in which specimens are built plays a paramount role in determining the morphological characteristics of the miniaturised components, resulting in significant variations in defect density distribution and morphology. However, the exploration of fatigue phenomena at the millimetric or sub-millimetric scale has been limited and insufficient to date (Murchio et al. [11], Murchio et al. [12], Persenot et al. [13] and Persenot et al. [14]).

Within this context, research efforts have typically centred on investigating axial fatigue strength at a specific single stress ratio. Nevertheless, a deeper understanding of the mean stress effect on fatigue properties of miniaturised specimens holds paramount importance for the intelligent design of complex lattice components. An illustrative example can be found in spinal prosthetic devices, where, despite the primary compressive load to which the overall component is subjected, various fatigue loading scenarios can affect individual struts. While a few studies have explored the mean stress effect on additively manufactured specimens (Cutolo et al. [15], Benedetti et al. [16], Derrick et al. [17] and Lietaert et al. [18]), to the best of the author's knowledge, an examination of the dependency on the building orientation of small-scale specimens remains uncharted territory.

This study aims to investigate and elucidate the relationship between the fatigue strength of L-PBF Ti6Al4V miniaturised strut-like specimens under different stress ratios and various building orientations, specifically at 90° , 45° , 15° , and 0° to the build plate. Initially, we employ an established in-house stereo-optical approach ([11], and Dallago et al. [19]) to detect the load-bearing cross-section of the specimens, assess their eccentricity, and evaluate their deviation from nominal designs. Following this initial assessment, we conduct an extensive fatigue testing campaign that encompasses four distinct fatigue regimens: tension-tension ($R=0.1$), tension-compression ($R=-1$), 25% tension-75% compression ($R=-4$), and compression-compression ($R=10$), each applied to specimens in the four building orientations mentioned earlier. The outcomes of this comprehensive campaign are then synthesised through Haigh diagrams. These diagrams consider the mean stress dependency of the specimens and facilitate the evaluation of predictive models, as well as their correlation with experimental data, gaining valuable insights into the fatigue life of L-PBF Ti6Al4V miniaturised components under varying loads and orientations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Miniaturised specimens

Miniaturised dog-bone specimens with a nominal thickness of 0.67 mm and a gauge length of 2.4 mm were designed and 3D-printed via L-PBF technology utilising biomedical-grade Ti-6Al-4V Grade 5 spherical powder (15-45 μm size range with controlled oxygen levels $O_2 < 0.2$). A transition section, designed according to the “stream-fillet approach” in Pilkey and Pilkey [20], was further added to prevent stress concentration factors at the gripping-gauge length interface. The printing of specimens was performed via an EOS M290 L-PBF printer equipped with a 400W laser and with layer thickness of 60 μm . The chosen L-PBF parameters aimed to balance productivity and accuracy in line with industrial requirements. Specimens have to be intended in an as-built condition, since any post-processing surface treatment was carried out after the heat treatment process (above 800°C) aimed at residual stress relieving and transforming the α -martensitic microstructure into a more stable $\alpha+\beta$ lamellar structure. Further details about the printing process can be found in [11]. Four differently oriented batches of thin-strut specimens were printed, namely at 90° , 45° , 15° and 0° with respect to the printing plate. Prior to any mechanical testing, thin struts were morphologically

characterised using an efficient stereo-optical method detailed in [11,19]. In summary, we utilised a Nikon SMZ25 stereo microscope to capture two images of each specimen. Image analysis was conducted using a custom MATLAB routine, keeping a sampling interval of 3.5 μm and extracting key geometric features such as strut thickness, cross-sectional area (with the assumption of elliptical area), eccentricity, and deviations from the as-designed geometry. Minimum and average cross-section of each thin-strut specimen were considered for the evaluation of the fatigue and buckling properties of the specimens.

Fatigue testing

The fatigue testing campaign was based on the exploration of four different stress regimes, defined as follows by the stress ratio, R. A fully reversible tension-compression fatigue cycle, R=-1, a tension-tension fatigue regime, R=0.1, a predominantly compressive (75%) fatigue cycle, R=-4, and a pure compression-compression fatigue regime, R=10. For each stress ratio, the S-N curves were built for the four different batches. Experiments were carried out with a Bose Electroforce 3200 testing machine equipped with a 200 N load cell. These tests operated at a nominal frequency of 200 Hz or 50 Hz (for the only case of R=10), with a sinusoidal waveform and a load-controlled regime. Runout specimens were set at 10⁷ cycles and a minimum of 12 samples for each condition and orientation were investigated. The stress amplitude at 50% failure probability has been fitted according to Eq. 1.1, while the 10%-90% failure probability bands according to Eq. 1.2:

$$\sigma_a = C_1 + \frac{C_2}{N_f^{C_3}} \quad (1.1)$$

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\sigma_{a,i} - \hat{\sigma}_{a,i})^2}{n-p} \quad (1.2)$$

Where N_f is the number of cycles at failure, C_1, C_2, C_3 the fitting coefficients, $\sigma_{a,i}$ is the i .th fatigue stress amplitude, $\hat{\sigma}_{a,i}$ its estimator and the parameters, n , and p , namely the number of collected data and the number of regression parameters of Eq. 1.1. Haigh diagrams for each building orientation were then generated considering the experimental data collected and correlating the stress amplitude at 10⁷ cycles with the corresponding mean stress, σ_m . Eq. 2.1-2.4 reports the four mean stress correlation models considered, namely the Godman-modified criterion (Eq. 2.1), the FKM method (Eq. 2.2), the Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) method (Eq. 2.3) and the Walker method (Equation 2.4).

$$\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_{a,eq}} + \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_{uts}} = 1 \quad (2.1)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \sigma_a(1 - M_\sigma) & \text{Region I} \quad R \geq -\infty \\ \sigma_a + M_\sigma \sigma_m & \text{Region II} \quad -\infty < R \leq 0 \\ (1 + M_\sigma) \frac{\sigma_a + \left(\frac{M_\sigma}{3}\right) \sigma_m}{1 + \left(\frac{M_\sigma}{3}\right)} & \text{Region III} \quad 0 < R \leq 0.5 \\ \sigma_a \frac{3(1+M_\sigma)^2}{3+M_\sigma} & \text{Region IV} \quad R > 0.5 \end{array} \right. \quad (2.2)$$

$$\sigma_{a,eq} = \sqrt{\sigma_{max} \sigma_a} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\sigma_{a,eq} = \sigma_{max}^{1-\alpha} \sigma_a^\alpha \quad (2.4)$$

Where $\sigma_{a,eq}$ is the equivalent amplitude stress, σ_{UTS} the ultimate tensile strength, σ_{max} the maximum stress under the fatigue regime and the M_σ mean sensitivity parameter, obtained considering the Ti6Al4V material parameters a_M and b_M respectively of 0.45 and -0.04.

Fractography images are collected for each stress ratio and building orientation by means of a Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) Zeiss Supra 40 (Zeiss, Germany) at 5.00 kV acceleration in a secondary electron mode,

Buckling

When compressed, as in the case of R=10 and R=-4 fatigue regimes, thin struts are prone and might fail due to buckling instabilities, prior to any fatigue-driven failure. Hence, the prediction of buckling onset is of paramount importance. Within this context, we employed the Johnson's elastic-plastic criterion (see Eq. 3), which appropriately apply for our specimen morphology, viz. short-intermediate columns.

$$\sigma_{cr} = \sigma_y - \frac{1}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_y}{2\pi} \right)^2 \left(\frac{l}{k} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

According to Johnson's criterion, the critical buckling stress, σ_{cr} , is dependent on the compressive yield strength, σ_y , the elastic modulus E , and the slenderness ratio of the strut $\frac{l}{k}$, with k as the radius of gyration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metrological characterisation

A comparison of geometric parameters obtained through stereo-optical metrological analysis is presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. Bar graphs display the minimum cross-section, average cross-section, and eccentricity data for different building orientations. Statistical tests, viz. One-Way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test, are conducted to identify, and explore significant differences among the four different batches.

As noticeable, vertically oriented specimens consistently exhibit disparities from less inclined struts, demonstrating the highest accuracy and shape fidelity with respect to the nominal design. In fact, the average cross section deviates by just $2 \pm 4\%$ from the nominal value, showcasing the closest adherence to the intended circular shape among the four batches. This is underscored by the low eccentricity value (0.26 ± 0.03). The enhanced shape fidelity and printing accuracy can likely be attributed to a more uniform solidification process and melt pool, in comparison to the other specimen orientations. In contrast, inclined and horizontal specimens are affected by the well-known "staircase" effect and by capillary and gravitational effects, resulting in more pronounced deviations from the nominal design and a departure from circular shapes. It is apparent that the average cross-section and eccentricity increase as the building orientation decreases, drifting apart from the nominal values. These variations and morphological fluctuations not only adversely affect geometric

properties but also impact the mechanical behaviour of miniaturised specimens. Indeed, higher geometrical fluctuations are also often associated with higher surface-to-volume ratio, increased defect sensitivity, waviness, and surface texture, as reported in [11] for similar miniaturised specimens.

TABLE 1 Geometric parameters obtained through the stereo-optical metrological analysis for the four building orientations.

	90°		45°		15°		0°	
	Minimum	Average	Minimum	Average	Minimum	Average	Minimum	Average
Cross section (mm²)	0.308 ± 0.016	0.347 ± 0.015	0.346 ± 0.051	0.405 ± 0.059	0.349 ± 0.062	0.448 ± 0.082	0.355 ± 0.067	0.461 ± 0.086
Dev. from CAD (%)	-13 ± 4	-2 ± 4	-2 ± 15	-15 ± 17	-1 ± 18	27 ± 23	1 ± 19	31 ± 24
Eccentricity	0.26 ± 0.03		0.52 ± 0.10		0.53 ± 0.09		0.57 ± 0.11	

FIGURE 1 – Cross-section and eccentricity average values over each batch are represented by mean bar chart plots along with their standard deviations. Average cross-section is represented by coloured bars, while minimum cross-section by coloured-patterned bars. Nominal as-designed strut area is graphed as a dash-dotted red line. Significance asterisks related to the post-hoc Tukey’s test are reported both for the cross-section and eccentricity data.

Buckling instabilities

TABLE 2 Compressive yield strength and analytic predictions for buckling load (N) and stress (MPa) for the four batches of miniaturised specimens.

	σ_y (MPa)	$c=0.5$		$c=0.65$	
		P_{cr} (N)	σ_{cr} (MPa)	P_{cr} (N)	σ_{cr} (MPa)
90°	630 ± 44	194 ± 11	602 ± 41	188 ± 11	582 ± 39
45°	486 ± 22	189 ± 7	470 ± 21	184 ± 7	459 ± 21
15°	492 ± 78	188 ± 36	474 ± 74	183 ± 35	462 ± 71
0°	514 ± 16	204 ± 23	495 ± 14	198 ± 22	482 ± 13

The prediction of critical buckling stresses holds paramount importance for lattice sub-unital elements, particularly for those predominantly exposed to high compressive loads, as seen in lattice-based spinal prosthetic devices. Eq. 3 has been employed to calculate predictive critical buckling stresses for the four batches, considering the yield strength obtained from experimental compression tests. Table 2 provides a summary the critical buckling stresses, considering two different coefficients, c , used to define the effective length of the struts: namely set at 0.5 and 0.65. As evident, vertical specimens report the highest critical buckling stress (602 ± 41 MPa) among the four batches. This superior buckling resistance can be closely linked to their higher printing accuracy and more circular cross-section. Parasitic masses and waviness, more commonly found in the other batches, can introduce local spurious bending moments, rendering the strut more prone to buckling instabilities. Regarding the other three orientations, no particular trend emerges. It is also noteworthy that the average cross-sectional values have been employed in the buckling prediction calculation. This choice aligns with the fact that buckling instabilities and more in general the monotonic properties of the struts are based on phenomena occurring at the entire specimen level, opposed to localised phenomena, such as fatigue, where the minimum cross-section is likely to be a more suitable descriptive parameter.

Fatigue behaviour

Figure 2 provides a comprehensive depiction of S-N curves on a semi-logarithmic scale, considering four distinct specimen orientations and stress ratios. Notably, stress amplitudes have been meticulously determined using the minimum cross-sectional area, a choice dictated by the localised nature of fatigue phenomena. This approach allows for a more accurate representation of crack initiation and propagation, especially within the narrowest valleys of thin-strut specimens where notches act as stress concentration points. A deeper exploration of this concept is available in [11].

In the tension-tension regime ($R=0.1$), it becomes evident that the fatigue performance is profoundly influenced by the orientation of the specimens. Thin struts oriented at 90° exhibit the highest fatigue strength, both in the low-cycle (LCF) and high-cycle (HCF) fatigue domains. In contrast, specimens oriented at 0° display the lowest fatigue strength across the entire range, establishing a clear inverse relationship: lower printing angles correspond to diminished fatigue life. This trend is likely attributed to the deteriorating quality of surface roughness texture as the building angle decreases, consistent with previous observations [11]. Indeed, cracks tend to propagate from

notches formed due to partially melted particles (Figure 3a) and cross-sectional variation-induced defects (Figure 3b) on the outermost specimen surfaces. Transitioning to the tension-compression regime ($R=-1$), the impact of orientation varies. Thin struts oriented at 0° continue to demonstrate the lowest HCF fatigue life (85 MPa), with the disparity from other curves becoming more pronounced. Surprisingly, specimens oriented at 90° no longer possess the highest HCF fatigue life (110 MPa), which is now observed in specimens oriented at 45° (118 MPa). In LCF, 90° struts still exhibit the highest fatigue strength (195 MPa), followed by 15° , 0° , and 45° specimens. It becomes evident that, in this regime, sensitivity to surface defects alone cannot fully account for fatigue strength. Porosity likely plays a synergistic role, especially in vertical specimens, where larger inner and sub-surface defects like Lack of Fusion (LoF) and gas holes may weaken the miniaturised specimen.

In the $R=-4$ condition, where compression constitutes 75% of the load and tension 25%, a distinctive orientation trend emerges. Notably, for this stress ratio, the orientation effect undergoes a complete reversal compared to $R=0.1$. Thin struts oriented at 90° now exhibit the lowest fatigue life (117 MPa), with a negative relative difference of approximately 20% from 45° specimens and 35% from 15° and 0° specimens. This change suggests a beneficial effect of compressive states in retarding surface crack nucleation and propagation from the surface, with a more substantial impact of internal and sub-surface defects in 90° specimens, as also noticeable from Figure 3c, where cracks propagate in the pore surrounding. The latter indeed report the highest defect density and largest sub-surface defects, as reported in the CT scan analysis in [11]. In the pure compression-compression regime ($R=10$), only the fatigue curve for specimens oriented at 90° could be constructed, as the other batches often experienced buckling instability prior to any fatigue failure. Vertical specimens fail due to the generation of multiple cracks along the strut gauge-length, mostly likely due to stress concentrations at the layer thickness ridges, as shown in Figure 3d. When the fatigue compressive load falls below the critical buckling stress, specimens reach a fatigue runout. Interestingly, fatigue life at 10^7 cycles follows a similar orientation trend as seen in $R=0.1$ specimens, wherein lower fatigue life corresponds to lower printing angles. These trends are clearly depicted in Figure 4, where it becomes evident how the stress ratio significantly influences the fatigue properties of the thin-strut specimens.

FIGURE 2 - Fatigue S-N curves for the four different stress ratios. Experimental data and the 50% failure probability fitting curve (dashed) and the 10%-90% scatter bands are reported for each building orientations. Vertical specimen fatigue data are depicted in red, 45° in yellow, 15° in light blue and 0° in dark blue. Coloured arrows indicate specimens which underwent runout at 10^7 cycles.

Particularly noteworthy is the observable increase in fatigue life at 10^7 cycles when transitioning from cyclic tensile to compressive fatigue regimes. This trend holds true for all four batches, aligning with findings from recent studies investigating the fatigue life of AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens under various stress ratios ([15-17], and Kelly et al. [21]). This increase can be attributed to the fact that tensile cyclic loads are more prone to accelerate fatigue failure due to their tendency to initiate cracks, leading to multiple crack initiation sites on the outermost surfaces of lattice struts. In contrast, compressive uniaxial loads can act as partial inhibitors of crack propagation, thereby extending the fatigue life of the specimens. While cracks may still initiate from the surface, internal defects and residual stresses assume more significant roles in determining fatigue failure [21]. Figure 4 also presents trends for the stress ratio ($R=10$), juxtaposing fatigue values at 10^7 cycles with the critical buckling stress for each building orientation. Critical buckling stresses (represented by dotted lines) were calculated by averaging critical buckling load stresses ($c=0.5$, as per Table 2) across all specimens in each batch, along with their standard deviation (depicted by coloured filled regions). This choice of the most critical c coefficient ensures an accurate prediction of buckling onset. In a compression-compression regime, the fatigue limit never surpasses the predicted buckling range, often falling within or below it, as observed in 90° and 0° thin struts. Consequently, the lower threshold of the critical buckling stress band can be considered a conservative reference for determining the buckling onset in thin-strut specimens.

FIGURE 3 - Fractography FE-SEM images displaying the main exemplificative fatigue failure modes observed in the four batches subjected to different loading conditions. A) and B) illustrate representative failures originating from the crack nucleation and propagation at the surface. A common occurrence in all specimens at $R=0.1$, and in inclined and horizontal specimens at $R=-1$ and at $R=-4$. Scale bar: $10\ \mu\text{m}$. C) illustrates cracks propagating from inner or sub-surface defects, a characteristic pattern observed in 90° subjected to a $R=-4$ fatigue regime. Scale bar: $10\ \mu\text{m}$. D) presents a 90° specimen failed at $R=10$, where cracks propagate along the gauge length at the layer thickness ridges. Scale bar: $20\ \mu\text{m}$.

FIGURE 4 Fatigue trends as function of the four building orientations at three different cycles to failure are reported. 10^5 , 10^6 , 10^7 cycles are respectively depicted by the light blue, dark blue and red curves. For $R=10$, the buckling onset (mean dotted line and upper and lower thresholds as full lines) are reported for each building orientation. The grey area indicates the region unsafe to buckling.

Figure 5 serves as a visual representation of Haigh diagrams corresponding to various building orientations. These diagrams encapsulate the experimental fatigue life data, which we previously delved into, across different stress ratios (R values of 0.1, -1, -4, and 10). They chart the 10^7 cycle data points, enclosing them within a 10% to 90% error band on a graph plotting stress amplitude (σ_a) against mean stress (σ_m). It is readily apparent that compressive stress regimes in inclined and horizontal struts substantially enhance fatigue life when contrasted with tension-tension fatigue. Among these orientations, the 15° and 0° orientations exhibit a greater sensitivity to mean stress compared to the 45° specimens. In contrast, vertical struts exhibit a milder effect due to factors such as porosity and internal defects. It is also noteworthy that we included the potential for buckling instability in these Haigh diagrams, as indicated by the coloured regions denoting where buckling failure could potentially occur. Figure 5 additionally includes dashed lines representing each investigated stress ratio. Furthermore, we have included an additional stress ratio, $R=\infty$, as it signifies the threshold below which the maximum stress becomes negative, marking the asymptotic line for the Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) and Walker predictive models.

These models, alongside the classic modified-Goodman and FKM approaches, are depicted for each Haigh diagram. Upon close examination, it becomes evident that the modified-Goodman

approach falls short in accurately capturing mean stress sensitivity, particularly when $\sigma_m < 0$. However, for 90° specimens, it aligns reasonably well with the $R=-4$ data. In the range where $\sigma_m > 0$, only the $R=0.1$ data for 90° specimens closely approximates the modified-Goodman curve. The FKM method and, to a greater extent, the Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) approach exhibit superior overall agreement across the spectrum of mean stress values. Among the models that do not necessitate a fitting process of the experimental data, SWT stands out as the most accurate criterion in most instances. In contrast, the Walker approach, which requires fitting experimental data, offers superior predictive capability for mean stress sensitivity.

In summary, even for miniaturised specimens, the trends observed through the predictive models reported herein closely align with previous studies on L-PBF Ti-6Al-4V specimens [15-17], wherein SWT and Walker approach emerge as the most suitable criteria for predicting mean stress sensitivity. It is worth noting that, from a design perspective, the Walker approach may not be the most ideal choice, due to the necessity to fit the experimental data to determine the coefficient α . However, it is intriguing to observe that the coefficient, $1-\alpha$, demonstrates a decreasing trend as the building angle increases. Higher values of $1-\alpha$ suggest greater sensitivity to defects, as discussed in [15], and can reasonably be associated with the diverse morphological outcomes observed for different building orientations, as discussed both here and in [11].

FIGURE 5 Haigh Diagram representing the fatigue life associated with 10^7 cycles for the four building orientations. Four predictive mean stress models are shown, namely SWT (red curve), Modified Goodman (blue curve), FKM (yellow curve) and Walker method (blue curve). The coefficient $1-\alpha$ for the latter are reported in a graph as function of the building angle. Buckling regions are indicated as filled coloured regions in the high diagrams.

CONCLUSIONS

This work explores the fatigue behaviour of Ti6Al4V L-PBF miniaturised specimens under varying stress ratios and building orientations. Stress ratios significantly impact fatigue life, with higher compressive loads extending fatigue life, due to the crack closure effects, hindering crack propagation from the surface. Building orientations exhibit distinct trends, depending on the stress ratio under investigation. In tension-tension scenarios, fatigue decreases from 90° to 0° thin struts. However, for R=-4, this trend reverses, with fatigue life increasing as the orientation moves from 90° to 0°. In the compression-compression regime, the trend shifts again, mainly due to buckling instabilities. This underscores the complex interplay of factors shaping the fatigue behaviour of thin struts, highlighting the importance of stress ratios, and building orientation in structural integrity assessment.

The investigation of mean stress effects using the Haigh diagram yielded interesting insights. Notably, the SWT method demonstrated superior alignment with experimental data compared to the modified-Goodman approach and the FKM method, emphasising the pivotal role of maximum stress in understanding fatigue behaviour. Moreover, the Walker method revealed varying mean stress sensitivity across the four building orientations. Particularly, a reverse correlation of the Walker's coefficient $1-\alpha$, with building orientation emerged, suggesting a lower mean stress dependency among vertical specimens due to their superior printing accuracy and reduced surface defects.

In summary, these findings offer valuable insights into predicting the fatigue behaviour of Ti6Al4V lattice structures, accounting for the different manufacturing outcomes and loading scenarios of the four batches. This work has the potential to guarantee a more informed design and manufacturing of next-generation lattice-based devices, particularly in the case of prosthetic devices, where struts experience different stress states (either tension or compression), despite the prevalence of compressive loads in their overall application.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

$C_{1,2,3}$	Fitting coefficients for the Wohler curves
$\frac{l}{k}$	Slenderness ratio
n	Number of collected experimental fatigue data
N_f	Number of cycles at fatigue failure
p	Number of fitting coefficients for the Wohler curves
σ_a	Stress Amplitude
$\sigma_{a,eq}$	Equivalent Stress Amplitude
$\hat{\sigma}_{a,i}$	Stress Amplitude estimator at the i^{th} cycle
σ_{cr}	Critical Buckling Stress
σ_m	Mean Stress
σ_{max}	Maximum Stress
σ_{UTS}	Ultimate tensile stress
σ_y	Yield Strength

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